

Aerodynamic Optimization of Freight Trains.

Part 2: Efficiency and safety recommendations from validated wind-tunnel experiments

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Abstract

In this work a method based on wind tunnel experiments is described to propose recommendations for aerodynamic optimized freight trains to improve energy efficiency and reliability. The sensitivity of a previous parameter drag study has been investigated against different upstream flow conditions using boundary layer argumentation. The wind tunnel measurements were compared to field test results gained by a real-world operational data acquisition system, the DLR's FR8-LAB. The results of this investigation are used to improve an incremental drag database, which is used to calculate the difference between the cumulative, aerodynamic drag of different loading schemes as well as estimate the energy and cost saving potential. The wind tunnel experiments were performed at a yaw angle of 0° and 5° to include crosswind effects and allow predictions for operational scenarios under realistic environmental conditions as well as safety related assessments. The experiments were performed in the Crosswind Simulation Facility at DLR Göttingen. The implementation of an iterative improvement of the drag database and validation with the use of the FR8-LAB's real-world data enables an evaluation for aerodynamic optimized rail freight transport with view on energy efficiency and safety in today's operation as well as forecasts and recommendations for future high-speed freight rail.

Keywords: freight, aerodynamics, drag, energy savings tool

1. Introduction

Aerodynamic optimization of freight trains is a crucial aspect for improving the energy efficiency and safety in today's and future freight rail operation. From the perspective of lowest CO₂ emission or carbon footprint, freight transport on rail is the best, climate-friendly solution for the constantly growing demand for green and sustainable transport of maximum freight over large distances on land. Especially at higher speeds in future rail freight operation, the importance of aerodynamic drag would increase dramatically. With a view on safety, aerodynamic optimized design aspects help reduce wind susceptibility, which can cause instability, particularly when freight trains travel through tunnels, over bridges, or in strong crosswinds.

This work is directly related to the acquisition of full-scale aerodynamic data from field tests in operational conditions using the DLR's FR8-LAB and presented at WCRR2025 in "Aerodynamic Optimization of Freight Trains. Part 1: Characterization of real-world operation from a full-scale measurement campaign", hereinafter referred to as "Part 1". The objective of this research is to develop a detailed drag database to be used in a calculation tool for potential energy savings with a view on loading schemes, cross-wind conditions as well as load and wagon specifications. Initial experiments with incrementally changed gap sizes on a generic freight train (Buhr et al., 2024) have already been conducted, providing valuable baseline data on drag for a functional tool to estimate energy savings depend on specific track speed profiles. The challenge of this research is to evaluate and optimize the drag database. The flow conditions around the model-scaled test container will be validated using the DLR's FR8-LAB, a 7.82m long test container for full-scale measurements in real world operation (Bell et al., 2022). This research includes advanced wind tunnel experiments focusing on operational loading configurations, validation with full-scale, field test

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results acquired by the FR8-LAB and the improvement of wind tunnel results using boundary layer argumentation. Comparable, aerodynamic investigations of loading configurations described in (Quazi et al., 2023) have shown, that the drag measured in a field study are up to 50% lower than in wind tunnel experiments and CFD simulations. The difference was suggested as sensitive to the modelling of real-world loading and environmental conditions. The work presented here focuses on the validation and improvement of the previously performed, incremental drag study and the gained drag database as well as the optimization of the energy savings estimation tool described in (Buhr et al., 2024).

This work is part of the EU-project TRANS4M-R funded by the European rail initiative Europe's Rail with multiple research groups and companies focussing on attractive, green and sustainable European rail freight of the future - specifically RENFE, ADIF and CEIT, who are already collaborating on improving freight train efficiency and safety operation. The described experimental capability in model-scale and real-world provides a strong basis for collaboration with new partners in the rail industry looking to improve the energy efficiency and safety by aerodynamic optimized rail freight transport.

2. Methodology

The experimental investigation of different loading configurations was performed in the crosswind simulation facility Göttingen (SWG). The wind tunnel was set-up for a Reynolds number of 5.5×10^5 in relation to the test container width, corresponding to an inflow velocity of ~ 50 m/s. Figure 1 shows the 1:15 scaled freight train model, consisting of an up-/downstream flow body and a modifiable gap test section around a test container on a highly simplified freight wagon base, placed on a generic single track with ballast and rail. The test container corresponds to a scaled model of the DLR's FR8-LAB, mounted on a six-component strain-gauge balance onto the freight wagon base to provide a decoupled measurement of the aerodynamic drag force. Furthermore, the test container was equipped with 254 pressure taps to investigate the flow development around the container. In the initial study with incremental change of the gap sizes (Buhr et al., 2024), the modifiable sections were filled with different sized blocks in order to vary the loading gaps up- and downstream. The filler part length corresponded to increments of the test container length, providing full-scale gaps of 0.156m up to 19.55m respectively 0.02 up to 2.5 times the

Figure 2: a) Generic freight train model installed in the SWG test-section, b) with boundary layer argumentation configuration BLA1 (LEGO®+spikes) and c) configuration BLA2 (LEGO®+larger spikes)

container length.

The wind tunnel setup was modified to use attachable boundary layer argumentation devices on the upstream flow body in the red circled section indicated in Figure 1. The two different boundary layer argumentation configurations, BLA1 & BLA2, are shown in Figure 2b, c compared to the clean configuration shown in Figure 2a. In both configurations about 2m of the upstream flow body sides and top starting at about 450mm flow body length were covered in roughness plates with more than 460 LEGO® 1x1 blocks + flat tile with dimensions of 8mm x 8mm base size and 10mm height. Additionally, a band of spikes was attached in front of the roughness plates. The size and spacing is the main difference between the two BLA-configurations: BLA1 spikes were 62mm long, 14mm base width, 32mm spacing; BLA2 spikes were 130mm long, 15mm base width, 48mm spacing.

3. Results

3.1 Validation of wind tunnel experiments with FR8-LAB field tests

As described in (Buhr et al., 2024), there is a variety of possible loading scheme gaps in real-world operation depending on spigot positions, buffer length, wagon length etc. The incremental drag study was

Figure 1: Wind tunnel setup of a generic freight train model in the Crosswind Simulation Facility Göttingen with variable, front/rear loading gap sizes and addable boundary layer argumentation.

performed to build up a drag database to use in an energy/cost savings calculation tool. The measured drag curves from the incremental study for up- and downstream (incr. GF, GR) are plotted separately in Figure 3a to visualize the different impact of front and rear gap as function of the gap size. In this study the respective other, not incrementally changed gap was kept fixed at 0.78m.

Within the frame of this work, three different gap configurations from the FR8-LAB field tests (Part 1) were used to compare the measured drag in full-scale and wind tunnel experiment: case #1 with 1.62m front/ 8.61m rear gap; case #2 with 8.68m front/ 1.62m rear gap and case #3 with 14.76m front/ 1.65m rear gap. Referring to (Buhr et al., 2024), the ~1.6m gap corresponds to a typical inter-car gap, the ~8.6m gap an empty slot on a wagon and the ~14.7m gap e.g. an (large) empty slot with inter-car gap. The wind tunnel drag results for these cases were determined using the interpolated drag database of the incremental gap study. The drag coefficients c_D of these test container cases from full-scale and wind tunnel tests are shown in Figure 3a as a function of the full-scale loading gap. It has to be noted, that these cases are plotted as function of the respective front gap size. This leads to the unexpected representation of the drag value for case #1 above the other graphs of the WT results, since in this case the rear gap with 8.68m has the main effect on the drag. The comparison between the results of Full-Scale and Wind Tunnel shows comparable drag values for case #1 with $c_D \sim 0.17$. For the cases #2 and #3, the FS drag values were significantly lower than WT by ~55% for case #2 (c_D of 0.2 to 0.44) and respectively by 47% for case #3 (c_D of 0.3 to 0.56). The difference between wind tunnel experiment and field tests corresponds to the results described in the study by (Quazi et al., 2023). The hypothesis is, that the oncoming flow condition, especially the boundary layer thickness does not match the conditions in the field tests. The boundary layer in a real-world operational train is assumed to be larger due to the different geometry of the locomotive, more structural roughness of the wagons and additional (inter-car) gaps upstream of the test container. The idea is to use boundary layer argumentation to increase the boundary layer thickness to improve the modelling of the upstream gaps and roughnesses in real-world like the locomotive and leading wagons.

Figure 3: a) Drag of the test container from FR8-LAB field tests (Full-Scale) compared to wind tunnel experiments (WT) with same gap configurations (cases) as well as incremental gaps in front/rear (incr. GF/GR) and symmetric gaps without and with boundary layer argumentation BLA1 and BLA2, b) corresponding surface pressure coefficient distributions from FR8-LAB and WT

3.2 Improved flow conditions with boundary layer argumentation

The initial investigation of the boundary layer argumentation effect in the configurations BLA1 and BLA2 have been performed with six symmetric (front=rear; GF=GR) gap configurations: 0.8m, 1.9m, 2.8m, 7.8m, 15.6m and 19.5m. The measured drag values without BLA (orange) and with BLA1 (red) or BLA2 (purple) are plotted in Figure 3a as function of the symmetric loading gap cases. The comparison of the three configurations shows a similar progression of the drag value in relation to the gap size, while the absolute drag values are about 25-35% lower with BLA1 and 30-40% lower with BLA2. Due to the increasing effect of the frontal gap with its size on the drag, the absolute effect of the BLA also increases and gets more significant with gaps larger than 3m. This observation corresponds to the matching drag values for the small gap case #1 between FS and WT. These results show, that the use of boundary layer argumentation

leads to the desired trend for an improved measurement of drag values. The exact configuration of the boundary layer argumentation in terms of size and spacing of the roughnesses will be optimized in further wind tunnel experiments. In the scope of this work a direct comparison of drag values without and with BLA between FS and WT is not possible, since the investigated BLA gap configurations does not match the example field test cases #1-#3, a direct correction and comparison is not yet possible, but will be in the frame of further, advanced WT measurements. Here, the symmetric gap configuration with similar front gap size for each case is used, since the front gap has the main impact on the drag, to analyse the effect of the BLA on the oncoming flow with view on the surface pressure distribution around the container as normalized pressure coefficients c_p . In Figure 3b the surface pressure distribution in the full-scale cases #1-#3 from (Part 1) is shown and compared against the pressure distribution of the WT cases with symmetric 1.9m gaps (#1), 8.6m gaps (#2) and 15.6m gaps (#3). The qualitative comparison between the FS cases and the symmetric WT cases without BLA shows a comparable pressure distribution: high pressure on the front and low-pressure regions in the front corners and on the sides due to flow separation corresponding to the flow structures developing around the container described in (Siegel et al., 2024). Especially notable the good agreement in case #1 with the small, inter-car gap, which leads to a characteristic, vertical pressure gradient/pattern on the front. The comparison between the WT cases without and with BLA1 and BLA2 shows, that the characteristic surface distribution is not affected by the BLA, but the absolute values of the pressure coefficient decreases with the size of the BLA. This observation corresponds to the hypothesis, that the BLA leads to a decreased oncoming flow speed through an increased boundary layer thickness without affecting the overall oncoming flow structure development. Therefore, the BLA is a suitable tool to improve future wind tunnel experiments. The implementation of the BLA will be determined with view on modelling realistic gaps in the upstream flow body and/or changing the roughness in size, shape and spacing.

3.3 Iterative optimization of energy savings estimation tool for real-world operation

The newly developed calculation tool provides a calculation of the difference in cumulative drag of a loading scheme derived from the different drag values of each single container, which is then used to estimate the energy and cost saving potential. Figure 4 shows an example process of estimating the difference in energy consumption between trains with different loading schemes (LS): a close-packed freight train (LS1), three empty slots (LS2), mixed wagon types & scattered load (LS3) and worst-case with one container per 3-slot wagon (LS4). A generic track speed profile was used as representation of a possible 300km freight route, with different sections with a train speed varying from 30km/h to a max speed of 120km/h, 160km/h or 200km/h. Based on the drag database, the cumulative drag coefficient of the load increases by $\Delta c_D \sim 1.62/5.81/15.25$ for LS2/3/4 respectively, which corresponds to an estimated additional energy consumption of 0.6/2.0/5.2MWh at 120km/h and significantly greater of 1.3/4.8/12.6MWh at 200km/h corresponding to 195/720/1890€ at 0.15€/kWh (Buhr et al., 2024). These estimations are based on the drag database without boundary layer argumentation. With advanced, more realistic wind tunnel experiments the accuracy of the estimation tool will be improved.

Figure 4: a) Four example loading schemes of a 660 m long freight train loaded with 24 containers, b) example of train speed track profile with c) estimated energy and cost savings potential

5. Conclusion

The outcome of the presented research is a calculation tool, which provides a simple integration of freight rail aerodynamics in a cost-benefit-analysis of train operators to enable a direct comparison with e.g. logistical costs, backed with direct validation from field measurements in operational conditions. Furthermore, this research gives recommendations for aerodynamic optimized freight trains and expected challenges for future high-speed rail freight transport. The newly developed calculation tool enables an evaluation for aerodynamic optimized rail freight transport with view on energy efficiency and safety in today’s operation as well as forecasts and recommendations for future high-speed freight rail. This research includes an iterative improvement of the drag database and validation with the use of the DLR’s FR8-LAB real-world data. The developed calculation tool and the recommendations for aerodynamic optimizations of freight trains will be made available for freight operators e.g. RENFE in Spain. Future improvements for the wind tunnel methodology are planned including an advanced, realistic model setup with variable model properties such as gaps in the upstream flowbody, a more realistic freight wagon design with detailed bogies, skirts and inter-car gaps featuring buffers and coupling systems, to generate more realistic flow conditions around the test container. The new measurements will be focused on discrete loading configurations of example wagons with typical container slots depending on original spigot positions. Furthermore, an advanced cross-wind study will be performed with a larger range of yaw angles to determine characteristic cross-wind polars to evaluate safety aspects with view on forces and moments.

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References

- Buhr, A., Siegel, L., Bell, J.R., and Henning, A., “Energy Savings for Freight Trains with Aerodynamically Optimized Loading Schemes”, In: Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Railway Technology: Research, Development and Maintenance, Civil-Comp Press, Edinburgh, UK, Volume CCC 7, Paper 3.2, 2024, doi:10.4203/ccc.7.3.2
- Bell, J.R., Buhr, A., and Henning, A., “Measuring the oncoming flow that operational freight-trains experience using the DLR FR8-LAB”, In: 23rd STAB/DGLR Symposium on New Results in Numerical and Experimental Fluid Mechanics XIV, 154, pp. 27-37. Springer Nature. 23. STAB-DGLR-Symposium 2022, 2022-11-09 - 2022-11-10, Berlin, Germany. doi:10.1007/978-3-031-40482-5_3. ISBN 978-3-031-40481-8. ISSN 1612-2909.
- Quazi, A, Crouch, T., Bell, J.R., McGreevy, T., Thompson, M.C., and Burton, D., “A field study on the aerodynamics of freight trains with different stacking configurations”, In: Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics, Volume 232, 2023, 105245, ISSN 0167-6105, doi:10.1016/j.jweia.2022.105245.
- Siegel, L., Buhr, A., Bell, J.R., and Henning, A., “Analysis of Flow Structures in Different Loading Gaps of Freight Trains”, In: Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Railway Technology: Research, Development and Maintenance, Civil-Comp Press, Edinburgh, UK, CCC7-3.1, 2024, doi:10.4203/ccc.7.3.1